

Local Governance as a Panacea for Democratic Stability and Sustainable Development in Nigeria's Fourth Republic: Myth or Reality?

Akinwande Olumuyiwa Opayinka

Department of Political Science, Obafemi Awolowo University, Nigeria

akinwandeopayinka11@gmail.com

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7892272

Abstract

This study examines local government as a vital way of achieving sustainable development at the grass root level since the inception of fourth republic in Nigeria. For any nation to be fully established, it must place premium on the existence of efficiency and equity of revenue mobilisation and public expenditure, integrity system and accountable public institutions, sustainability of economic transformation, corporate and entrenched rules that promote sustainable development, protect human rights, respect the rule of law and ensure that the people are free to participate in the decisions that affect their locality. Therefore, the objective of the study was to identify the extent of socioeconomic factors that influences against sustainable development in Nigeria since the inception of fourth republic, as well as the extent of local government as an effective strategy towards achievement of sustainable development at the grass root level in Nigeria's fourth republic. Methodologically, both qualitative and quantitative techniques of data gathering were adopted. Subsequently, content analysis was employed in the interpretation of documents, reports, and publications obtained from the Non-State Actors (NSA), and Community Stakeholders. Finding from this study revealed that widespread corruption, leadership idiosyncrasy and personal mannerism, unproductive or inefficient agricultural practice, low level of industrialisation, inappropriate development policies, acute poverty, dearth of integrity system and accountability are the socioeconomic factors that influences against the sustainable development to be functioning with the local government administration at the grass root levels since the inception of fourth republic in Nigeria. The study, therefore, recommends that local government administration in Nigeria cannot be successfully address the socioeconomic factors that influences sustainable development at the grassroots levels unless the constitution strengthening the levels of democratic institution that uphold the sanctity of justice, equity and accountability of rules of law at all times.

Keywords: Local governance, Governance, Sustainable development, Development

Introduction

Local government plays a significant role in achieving sustainable development since the inception of fourth republic in Nigeria. It is very much interlinked with institutionalised democratic values such as common decision making (popular participation), fundamental human rights, rules of law and greater efficiency and effectiveness within their public interests, or a device for sustainable development, (Onyekachi, 2013). The issue of local government is a phenomenon that have affected the growth of many developing nations with respect to Africa and Nigeria in Particular; since the inception of fourth republic in 1999, Nigeria has battled with the issue of bribery and widespread corruption, leadership idiosyncrasy and personal mannerism, ambiguities in the 1999 constitution, low level of industrialisation, inappropriate development policies, acute poverty, lack of inequitable distribution of income, dearth of employment opportunity, lack of infrastructural facilities and dearth of integrity system and public accountability in the local government system. The search for local governance seems to be Nigeria's most urgently need under the current democratic dispensation, (Kabumba, 2015).

Furthermore, Nigerians believe strongly that the socioeconomic factor that had crippled the sustainable development in virtually every aspect of human effort is leadership idiosyncrasy and personal mannerism, acute poverty, low level of industrialisation, inappropriate development policies, inequitable distribution of income, rising of unemployment, and widespread corruption, (Ebikeme, 2017). The ultimate desire of human beings, wherever they find themselves is to enjoy certain level of good life sustenance and quality improving service delivery. As a result, all nations aspire to attain rapid economic transformation and sustainable development that will ensure that the citizenry enjoy better conditions of democratic stability (Onyeoma, 2014).

Moreover, in the recent past, it was observed that local government in Nigeria has undergone series of transformation. This system has been restructured, reorganised and revitalised depending on the regime in power, as well as the nature and level of interest of sure regime in local government administration. But since the inception of fourth republic in 1999, there has been no significant improvement in terms of local governance in Nigeria as widespread corruption has been on the increase. There is high rate of unemployment, no access to basic infrastructural facilities and public health care, high rate of crimes and above all poverty has been ravaging the society (Omeiza, 2018).

Finally, for local government to able to contribute meaningfully and play their roles effectively toward the attainment of sustainable national development in Nigeria, there is need for sustainability of structural economic transformation reforms or plans and public institutional control processing system that will make impact positively on the citizens and contribute to socio-economic factors, that will address the challenges and reduce them to the minimum. If these are done, they will undoubtedly enhance the prospects of local government for helping to deepen and consolidate democracy and contribute to sustainable development in Nigeria fourth republic, (Akhakpe, 2012).

Statement of the problem

The attainment of sustainable development since the inception of fourth republic in Nigeria remains paramount at the grassroots levels through the local government system. The pursuit of sustainable development will not be attainable without alleviating poverty drastically, empowering the Nigerian citizens in various endeavours and careers; encouraging sustainable development for productive employment; achieve gender equality, sustainable consumption and production pattern. It is believed that the attainment of these goals will set the Nigerian economy on the pedestrian of socio-economic growth and development in this present democratic dispensation (Hope, 2015).

Objectives of the study

The major objective for this study is to determine the strategy for achieving sustainable development on local governance in Nigeria's fourth republic.

Other specific objective included:

- i. identifies the extent of socio-economic factors that influences against sustainable development in Nigeria since the inception of fourth republic; and
- ii. examine the extent of local government as an effective strategy towards achievement of sustainable development at the grass root level in Nigeria's fourth republic.

Conceptual exploration of the study

The main concepts discussed in this paper relate to Governance, Local Governance, Development, and Sustainable Development. Detailed explanation of the above concepts-based on the opinion of scholars is provided below;

Governance

The World Bank (1989) asserts that governance is “the exercise of political power to manage a nation's affairs”. Three distinct aspects of governance are identified to include: the form of political regime; the process by which authority is exercised in managing a country's economic and social resources for development; and the capacity of governance to design, formulate and implement policies and discharge functions.

Local Governance

United Nations Development Programmes (2014) postulates that local governance is the political mechanism, processes and institution through which the citizen and a group of citizens articulate their public interest, needs and their legal right or obligation from the government within their state. Local governance is made up of instrument and elements including: quality leadership, bureaucratic

capacity, efficiency and equity, service delivery and non-corrupt judiciary enforcing the rule of law, popular participation, fundamental human right, and democratic institutional system.

Development

According to the World Rio Declaration on Environment and Development (2010), Development can be defined as multi-dimensional processes that involve different goals of social, political, economic, and technological transformational change within the society.

Sustainable Development

According to the Sustainable Development Report (2015), sustainable development is a development that meets the current needs of the people without compromising the ability of the future generations to meet their own needs. It contains within it two key concepts:

- i. the concept of needs, in particular, it is the essential needs of the world's poor, to which overriding priority should be given; and
- ii. the idea of limitations imposed by the state of technology and local industrialisation on the environment's ability to meet present and future needs.

Theoretical exposition of the study

The most appropriate theoretical context for this study is participatory theory. This theory describes the relevant of the entire citizen to participate in decision-making processes within the society. As postulated by Kurt Lewin's and Henry A. Bryman, participatory theory seeks to explain the important of community development benefit and decision-making processes among the people within the state (society).

Relevance

The theory emphasises that the common decision-making process involves a large number of people. This format encourages other participants to share their thoughts, ideas, and concerns. The most crucial aspect is that it keeps everyone informed.

Strength

The theory's notable advantages; everyone is given a voice, it gives every citizen a sense of accountability, it increases morale, and it can help one to learn more about his/her community. Participatory theory can be a sham when rulers seek for popular participation and opinion disregarded. Such act can result to scepticism and feelings of unfaithfulness.

Limitation

The theory is very useful because development requires a bottom-top approach that involves people of different strata and this leads to the adoption of the theory for the study. The main goal of sustainable development is to move gender equality, and material resources toward development via effective mobilization of both human and material resources, as well as active participation of the rural population (Albrow, 2013)

Methodology

This study adopted a mixed method research design, through the use of primary and secondary sources of gathering relevant information and materials subsequently, content analysis was employed to analyse the socio-economic factors that influences against local government towards achievement of sustainable development at the grass root level (locality) in Nigeria's fourth republic.

Study area

This study was conducted in Osun State Nigeria. Three local government areas (LGAs) were randomly selected among the local government areas in Osun State. That is, one metropolis, one urban and one semi urban to serve as representative sample of the LGA in the State.

Sampling procedure and sample size

The sample size for this study are the staff of Osun State Local Government Service Commission, Community Development Association, and Non-state actors within the three selected local

government areas and local government employees in selected LGA. The Local Government Areas are Osogbo LGA, Ede South LGA, and Ife North LGA. In selecting the respondents, a total of 130 respondents were sampled in each selected LGAs of Osun State. Consequently, a total of 390 respondents were sampled. Data were gathered from each of these selected areas. Out of the 390 copies of questionnaire administered, only 381 copies were retrieved from field, and after going through them 381 copies (approximately 98% response rate) were found useful for data analysis.

Analytical procedure

Frequency distribution tables and percentages were used to analyses socio-economic factors of local government that militates against the sustainable development in Nigeria. The socio-economic parameter included bribery and widespread corruption, acute poverty, low level of industrialisation and infrastructural facilities, dearth of employment opportunity, inequitable distribution of income and inappropriate development policies framework and strategies by government.

Analysis of discussion and presentation of result

Research question 1

To what extent does local government influences sustainable development in selected local government area of Osun State.?

Table 1: The extent to which local government influences sustainable development in selected local government area

<i>Options</i>	<i>Number of respondents</i>	Percentage/Response
Very large extent	91	24%
Large extent	103	27%
Moderate extent	76	20%
Low extent	65	17%
Very low extent	46	12%
Total	381	100%

Source: Survey Data, 2022

Table 1 shows that 24% of the respondents indicated that to a very large extent local government influences sustainable development in selected local government area, 27% of them indicated ‘to a large extent’ while 20% of them indicated to a moderate extent to the question. Equally, 17% of the respondents indicated to a low extent to the question while only 12% of them indicated that to a very low extent local government encourage sustainable development in selected local government areas.

Research question 2

To what extent do socio-economic factors (bribery and widespread corruption, lack of infrastructural facilities, poverty, dearth of employment opportunity, constraint of public funds, low level of industrialisation, lack of infrastructural facilities and inequitable distribution of income) of the citizens in selected local government areas affect their efforts in achieving sustainable development in Nigeria’s fourth republic from 2020-2022?

Table 2: The extent to which socio-economic factors influence the citizens in selected local government areas in achieving sustainable development from 2020-2022

Options	Number of Respondents	Percentage Response
Very large extent	107	28%
Large extent	91	24%
Moderate Extent	80	21%
Low Extent	61	16%

Very low extent	42	11%
Total	381	100%

Source: Survey Data, 2022

The data in table 2 revealed that 28% of the respondents indicated to a very large extent that socio-economic factors (bribery and widespread corruption, lack of infrastructural facilities, poverty, dearth of employment opportunity, constraint of public funds, and inequitable distribution of income) affected the citizens in selected local government areas and their efforts in achieving sustainable development from 2020-2022. Equally, 24% of them showed to a large extent while 21% of the respondents indicated to a moderate extent that the socio-economic factors of the citizens in selected local government area affected their efforts in achieving good governance from 2001-2012. The data further revealed that 16% of the respondents indicated that to a low extent socio-economic factors of the citizens in selected local government area affected their efforts in achieving sustainable development from 2020-2022, while only 11% of them indicated to a very low extent.

Research question 3

To what extent does local government influence the socio-economic empowerment of the citizens to achieve sustainable development in selected local government areas of Osun State?

Table 3: The extent to which local government influences the socio-economic empowerment of the citizens to achieve sustainable development in selected local government areas of Osun State

Options	Number of Respondents	Percentage/Response
Very large extent	91	24%
Large extent	160	42%
Moderate Extent	88	23%
Low extent	30	8%
Very low extent	12	3%
Total	381	100%

Source: Survey Data, 2022

The data in Table 3 show that 24% of the respondents agreed that to a very large extent local government influences the economic empowerment of the citizens in selected local government area of Osun State. Also 42% of them indicated to a large extent, while 23% of them indicated that to a moderate extent local government influence the economic empowerment of the citizens in selected local government areas of Osun State. Equally, 8% of the respondents indicated to a low extent to the question while only 3% of them indicated to a very low extent that local government influences the economic empowerment of the citizens.

Research question 4

What are some of the challenges that influence local government, sustainable development and as well causing the economic empowerment of the citizens in selected local government areas of Osun State?

Table 4: Challenges militating against local government, sustainable development and the economic empowerment of the citizens in selected local government area of Osun State

Options	Number of Respondents N = 381	Percentage Response	Rating
Constraint of public funds to execute local government programmes	354	93%	2nd
Dearth of employment opportunities	366	96%	1st
Bribery and widespread corruption	293	77%	6th
Lack of Infrastructural facilities	354	93%	2nd

Low level of industrialisation & infrastructural	324	85%	3rd
Inappropriate of development policies Framework and strategies by government	354	93%	2nd
Inequitable distributable of income	312	82%	5th
Acute Poverty	316	83%	4th

Source: Survey Data, 2022

Table 4 shows that one of the socio-economic factors influencing local government, sustainable development and the economic empowerment of the citizens in selected local government areas of Osun State is ‘dearth of employment opportunities’ as 96% of the respondents indicated this, thereby placing the option first among others. ‘Constraint of public funds to execute local government programmes’ and ‘inappropriate of development policies framework and strategies by government’ ranked second in the rating as 93% of the respondents indicated them. Followed by some socio-economic factors influencing against local government, sustainable development and the economic empowerment of the citizens in selected local government areas of Osun State is the “low level of industrialisation’ indicated by 85% of the respondents, thereby placing them third in the ranking. The fourth socio-economic factors influencing local government, sustainable development and the economic empowerment of the citizens in selected local government area of Osun State is ‘Acute poverty’ identified by 83% of the respondents. The fifth socio-economic factors influencing against local government, sustainable development and the economic empowerment of the citizens in selected local government area of Osun State is ‘inequitable distribution of income’. Finally, the respondents (77% of them) identified ‘Bribery and widespread corruption’ as the sixth socio-economic factor influencing local government, sustainable development and the economic empowerment of the citizens in selected local government areas of Osun State.

Test of hypothesis

The hypothesis states that “There is no significant relationship between the socio-economic factors influencing local government area and their efforts in achieving sustainable development in Nigeria’s fourth republic.

Table 5: Statistical relationship between socio-economic factors influencing local governance and sustainable development in Nigeria’s fourth republic

Socioeconomic Factors	Local Governance (X)	Sustainable Development (Y)	X ²	Y ²	XY
Dearth of Employment	89	91	7921	8281	8099
Constraint of public Funds	162	103	26244	10609	16686
Low Level of Industrial	85	76	7225	5776	6460
Acute Poverty	32	65	1024	4225	2080
Inequitable of Income	13	46	169	2116	598
Total	381	381	42583	31007	33923

Source: Survey Data 2022

*r = 0.945 (positive relationship) t = 5.16
(very significant) t crit @ 3; 0.05 = 3.18

The data in table 5 are drawn to see whether there is significant relationship between socioeconomic factors influencing against local governance and sustainable development. From the statistical presentations above and the values of r computed (i.e. 0.945) and t computed (i.e. 5.16). It is obvious that the computed t value is greater than the figures obtained from the table, which are

3.18. Therefore, ‘there is positive/significant relationship between socio-economic factors influencing against local governance and sustainable development in Osun State Nigeria.

Local government as an effective strategy towards achievement of sustainable development at the grassroots level in Nigeria’s fourth republic

The local government administration has important role to play in the attainment of sustainable development in Nigeria, impact positively on the citizens, and contribute to development to their locality (Caroline, 2018). Most countries that are similar in terms of socioeconomic factors and technological innovation with Nigeria have shown strictly different performance in improving their economic transformation and build effective welfare of their citizens. This has been attributed to standards of quality improvement service delivery which stifles and impedes sustainable development. A nation where there is a widespread corruption, inadequacy of public funds, low level of industrialisation, acute poverty and dearth of employment opportunity can never achieve sustainable development. Local government should play a crucial role to achieve sustainable national development at the grass root levels in Nigeria since inception of fourth republic (Aransi, 2010).

Rapid economic transformation and sustainable development will remain a mirage so long as the government process and institutions that guarantee accountability and transparency; rule of law and security of the citizens are either absent or rudimentary (Grindle, 2017). Finally, the achievement of the sustainable development in Nigeria will depend to a very large extent on the citizens particularly those in the position of authority having the ability to suppress their selfish interest in favour of the nation’s interest and development (Kemp, 2015).

Therefore, the following strategies are suggested for the local government toward the attainment of sustainable development in Nigeria:

- i. The government should enthrone the democratic institutional control processing mechanism of accountability and rules of law that allow the legislature to enact laws; while the judiciary should be given the enabling environment to interpret same and deal with offenders irrespective of primordial affiliations without interference.
- ii. There should be the entrenchment of government policies implementation framework and enforceable rules that will ensure that the nation’s resources are developed for the benefits of all citizens irrespective of tribe and political affiliation.
- iii. Corruption should be tackled with anti-corruption strategies that may include: zero tolerance for corruption and other economic crimes; hence inefficiency and ineffectiveness in governance should be eliminated through reform of government agencies, discipline and exemplary leadership.
- iv. Efficiency and equity of public investment process and expenditure should be maintained in every sector, which is both the private and public sectors.

Conclusion

Moreover, local government administration in Nigeria cannot successfully address the socioeconomic factors that influence sustainable development at the grassroots levels unless the constitution strengthens the levels of democratic institution that uphold the sanctity of justice, equity and accountability of the rule of law at all times. This will make the nature of local governance provide the needs for sustainable development strategy and the achievement of outcomes such as sustainability, participation, equity, accountability and transparent as it they affect the citizens living in the rural areas and their locality. The local government has the capacity to design the policy implementation framework formulation strategies and equitable sound development management which will meet the needs of current generation without compromising the future. Local governance is the foundation of development; hence it is a pivot for sustainable development. Though there are no perfect governing structures and institutions but they can be continuously improved

Recommendation

The following specific recommendations are therefore germane:

- i. There should be an effective democratic institutional control processing mechanism and systems that are responsive to public expenditure management and investment process, needs, and service delivery that promote economic development.
- ii. Democratic institutions should manifest the spirit of accountability, responsiveness and control that will allow local government to performance a range of functions.
- iii. Both effective management and well-functioning markets require that there should be clear rules about what constitute acceptable conducts in the realm of economic, social and political life. Hence strict enforcement of the rule of law to all citizens should not be based on ethnicity and political affiliation.
- iv. There should be full inclusive citizenship based on the respect of gender, culture, religion and other differences.

References

- Abubakar, H. I. (1993), "Local government and development in Nigeria". *Journal of public administration and management*, 2 (7), 38-44.
- Afegbua, S. I., & Adejuwon, K. D. (2012), The challenges of leadership and governance in Africa. *International journal of academic research in business and social sciences*, 2 (9), 141-157.
- Agbodike, F.C., Igbokwe-Ibeto, C.J. and Nkah, B.C. (2014), "Local government administration and the challenges of sustainable development in Nigeria", *Review of public administration and management*, 3 (6), 96-105.
- Akhakpe, I., Fatile, J.O. and Igbokwe-Ibeto, C.J. (2012), "Local government and the challenges of community and rural development in Nigeria: the way forward", *International journal of asian social science*, 2 (6), 648-665.
- Akinroye, K. K. (2016), "Health and sustainable development goals in Nigeria road to 2030". *In ife social sciences review (special issue) on Environmental and sustainable development in 21st century. Ile-ife, The faculty of social sciences*, Obafemi Awolowo university xvii.
- Albrow, M. (2013), Good Governance practice for better performance of community organisation. *Journal of power, politics and governance*, 1(9), 60-78.
- Alesina, A., Ozler, S., Roubini, N., & Swagel, P. (2016), Political instability and economic growth. *Journal of economic growth*, 1 (2), 189-211.
- Aransi, I. O. (2010), "Status and roles of local government as an aspect of public administration in Nigeria". *African journal of institution and development (AJID)*, 7 (8), 72-97.
- Brundtland Commission (1987), Our common future: Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development. *UN Documents Gathering a Body of Global Agreements*.
- Caroline, A. (2018), From local government to local governance beyond. *International political science review*, 19 (2), 55-87.
- Dormbos, M. (2014), Good governance the rise and decline of a policy metaphor. *International journal of development studies*, 37 (6), 96-108.
- Gilbert, L. D., & Allen, F. (2017). Democracy and good governance: The missing link in Nigeria. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5 (16), 524-531.
- Grindle, M. S. (2012), Good enough governance: Poverty reduction and reform in developing countries. *International journal of governance studies*, 17 (4), 525-548.
- Hope, K. R. (2015), Towards good governance and sustainable development: The African peer review mechanism. *An International journal of policy, administration, and institutions*, 18 (2), 283-311.
- Kabumba, I. (2015), Good governance and sustainable development in Africa: Meaning, relationship, problems and strategies. *African Journal for Public Administration and Management*, 9(6), 78–101.

- Kemp, R., Parton, S., & Gibson, R. B. (2015), Governance for sustainable development: Moving from theory to practice. *International journal of sustainable development*, 8 (1-2), 12-30.
- Mebratu, D. (2018), Sustainability and sustainable development: Historical and conceptual review. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 18 (6), 493–520.
- Meadowcroft, J. (2017), Who is in charge here? Governance for sustainable development in a complex world. *Journal of environmental policy & planning*, 9 (3-4), 299-314.
- Omeiza, M. D. (2018), Rethinking good governance and democratization for sustainable development in Africa. *International journal of academic research in social science*, 4 (6), 34-47.
- Onyekachi, O. D. (2013), Good governance A catalyst to sustainable development. *Afro Asian journal of social sciences*, 4 (4), 1-10.
- Plumptre, T., & Graham, J. (1999), Governance and good governance: International and Aboriginal perspectives. *International journal of governance studies*, 8 (5), 81-106.
- Potter, D. (2010), Democratization, good governance, and development. In T. Allen, & A. Thomas (Eds.), *Poverty and development into the 21st Century*, (365-382). Oxford, England: Oxford University Press.
- Rio declaration on environment and development, (2010), Report of the united nations conference on environment and development, united nations general assembly.
- Sebudubudu, D. (2010), The impact of good governance on development and poverty in Africa: Botswana-A relatively successful African initiative. *African journal of political science and international relations*, 4 (7), 249-262.
- United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs (2013). *World economic and social survey 2013: Sustainable development challenges*. New York, NY: Author.
- United Nations Development Program (2014), *Governance for sustainable human development*. New York, NY: United Nations Development Program.
- World Bank, (1989), *It's not only about Good governance development outreach*, 2014.